

The Public's Reliance on Digital Platforms Supported by Artificial Intelligence Technologies as a Source of Information about Natural Disasters

"The Moroccan Earthquake is an Example" "A Field Study."

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Abstract

The Study aimed to identify the rate of public dependence on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies as a source of information about natural disasters. It used the descriptive approach in the style of a sample survey as a tool for collecting data. The sample consisted of (500) individuals from Egyptian and Jordanian citizens following the Moroccan earthquake disaster. The results reached: There is a statistically significant correlation between the rate of public reliance on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the follow-up of the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster. This indicates that the greater the reliance on digital news platforms supported by technologies, the greater the follow-up to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster; in addition, there are statistically significant differences between the forms of interaction of sample members with topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies according to the geographical distribution variable, and in the direction of the Egyptian audience, which indicates: the influence of news content on the importance of audience interaction with the news—transforming a receiver into a sender and sharer of information on his page.

Keywords: digital platforms, artificial intelligence, natural disasters.

Introduction

Digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies have contributed to the emergence of new and innovative communication patterns that have helped provide many news services to the public thanks to the reliance on simulation robots that carry out the tasks of news coverage of current events, such as producing, photographing and editing news content in text and images in a language that simulates human intelligence as a result of dealing with big data accurately. Furthermore, it quickly develops and upgrades the news system thanks to simulation robots that broadcast news content related to current events.

Due to the increasing use of artificial intelligence technology, media institutions have tended to adopt alternative solutions due to the challenges imposed by digital developments on the news industry. Interactive digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies have become a fertile media environment for performing the human tasks and roles that constitute the media production chain. These platforms have helped increase The transmission of news and information related to current events to the public more interactively, especially in times of crisis, and in particular, the publication of topics related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, which led to the creation of a media environment based on interaction, dialogue, and participation between users and chatbots based on digital news platforms supported by tools.

Artificial intelligence on topics related to the Moroccan earthquake disaster aims to enrich interactive discussions and exchange opinions about it between users, each other, and those in charge of these platforms. Therefore, researchers found the need to conduct a study to determine the public's dependence on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies as a source of information about natural disasters.

Literature Review

Previous studies varied between studies that were interested in studying the public's dependence on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies to follow current events and others that were interested in forms of interaction with topics related to them on those sites, and when researchers reviewed studies related to the research topic, it was found that: There are many studies which emphasized the nature of the relationship between the rate of public follow-up to topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the interactivity of those platforms. The studies were arranged descending from newest to oldest as follows:

Muhammad (2024) aimed to identify the level of public awareness of the impact of algorithmic systems on the distribution of news content on Facebook and its relationship to their interactive behavior; the results revealed that the sample members have a high awareness of the algorithmic systems that distribute news content on Facebook platforms, despite their insufficient awareness of the existence of interventions. A human being behind this machine can influence the decisions of the content presented.

Abdel Basset (2023) examined the role of digital media in raising awareness of the issues of artificial intelligence technologies as a concept in the areas of their employment and the impact this had on Egyptian youth, specifically testing the presence of acceptance of artificial intelligence technologies technology, which results in shaping the Egyptian public's awareness of these technologies, and the results showed that individuals in the sample interact with the media messages that include products and services that rely on artificial intelligence technologies.

Makady (2023) identified the role of digital platforms supported by algorithms in educating and encouraging the public to consume news and interact with it actively. The results revealed a relationship between

algorithmic awareness, self-monitoring, and active news consumption on Facebook, which indicates the mediating role of self-monitoring that levels of algorithmic awareness encourage active consumption when the risks of self-presentation on the platform are high.

Nechushtai et al. (2023) explored the extent of the ability of digital platforms equipped with algorithmic systems "Facebook, YouTube, Twitter" to help American participants in searching for news; the results showed that there are differences between individuals in the sample in political orientations towards the topics presented and that professionally produced news on some platforms constitutes the basic pillars which rely on the political orientations of the public in searching for information, such as Fox News in particular.

Abdel Ghaffar (2022) investigated the mechanisms and forms of audience interaction with reports of a social nature on the digital platforms of foreign Arabic-speaking channels. The results revealed a statistically significant relationship between the availability of interactive tools and the way the respondents interacted with reports of a social nature published on the digital platforms of foreign Arabic-speaking channels.

Wood (2021) aimed to identify the measurement of influencers' content across social media sites and the interaction strategy, which means the number of followers, the size of the content, and the areas of interest. The results revealed a significant positive interaction between the volume of content and areas of interest, which indicates that influencers with diverse interests can stimulate greater participation of followers by sharing more content on their social media accounts.

Comment on previous studies and the limitations of benefiting from them:

Through the researcher's review of previous scientific heritage, the researchers noted the following:

- The Arab and foreign schools agreed on the importance of the interactivity of social media, as it is a means that allows the user

to interact with media content that includes various topics related to current events. It is a characteristic of both the medium and the user due to its ability to provide the public with information by providing the latest developments related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster. From the event site and broadcast on digital news platforms.

- Literature reviews represented a rich scientific resource from which researchers derived a sound scientific vision for the subject of the Study. Previous studies also contributed to identifying some important informational dimensions that take up part of the cognitive framework of the Study. By reviewing previous studies, it is clear that they helped researchers as follows:
 - 1- Forming a clear vision of the research problem regarding its definition, formulation, and general framework.
 - 2- Help determine the appropriate scientific method and tools for collecting data.
 - 3- Determine the study sample and its applied field.
 - 4- Determining the appropriate theoretical framework for the nature of the Study, represented in the theory of "symbolic interactionism," entails the ability to formulate questions and define the field study population and how to draw a sample from it.
 - 5- Formulating the Study's hypotheses and questions scientifically to achieve its objectives based on the results.
 - 6- Utilizing it in designing the questionnaire sheet.
 - 7- Utilizing them in analyzing, interpreting, and commenting on the results in a correct scientific manner, as the theoretical frameworks of previous studies that were commented on in the current study are linked to the public's reliance on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies as a source of information about natural disasters "the Moroccan earthquake."

The Problem Statement

Due to the growing role played by artificial intelligence applications in creating digital content, media organizations have tended to take advantage of technologies supported by artificial intelligence tools to carry out various tasks more quickly by producing news content related to current events and presenting them to the public in a language that simulates human intelligence with text, audio, and images. Artificial intelligence technologies are an important source for the public to obtain news and information related to current events in times of crisis, especially the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, which led to the destruction of heritage buildings, homes, and basic road infrastructure, in addition to the high numbers of deaths and injuries.

These platforms have formed a fertile environment for creating discussion. Interactive, based on dialogue and participation between the public and chatbots based on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence tools on topics related to the Moroccan earthquake disaster, to know the most important news and present different visions and ideas to confront that disaster. Therefore, the problem of the Study is crystallized in the following main question: **What is the rate of public dependence on the platforms?** Digital technology supported by artificial intelligence as a source of information about natural disasters? In light of the social presence of the audience on interactive news platforms supported by artificial intelligence tools to follow the content provided to them on the network.

Research Questions

- 1- What is the relationship between the rate of public dependence on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the follow-up of the "Morocco earthquake" disaster?
- 2- What is the relationship between the public's follow-up of specific topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster

through digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the degree of benefit from them?

- 3- What are the differences between the sample members' forms of interaction with topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies according to the geographical distribution variable?

The Hypotheses

To achieve the objectives of the Study and answer its questions, the study hypotheses were represented in three main hypotheses, which are:

- 1- There is a statistically significant correlation between the rate of public reliance on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the follow-up of the "Morocco earthquake" disaster.
- 2- There is a statistically significant correlation between the public's follow-up of specific topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the degree of benefit from them.
- 3- There are statistically significant differences between the sample members' forms of interaction with topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies according to the geographical distribution variable.

The Significance of the Study

- **The theoretical importance is due** to the focus on the rate of public dependence on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies to follow the Moroccan earthquake disaster, as it is an important media tool that benefits the public in knowing the current events related to it, especially in light of the global interest in that disaster that led to the destruction of heritage buildings and homes and basic road infrastructure, in

addition to the hundreds of deaths and injuries and the recovery of more bodies from under the rubble, which caused economic losses estimated at billions of dollars, which reflects the importance of these platforms in knowing the patterns of interaction with opinion and other opinions towards dialogue and participation.

- **As for the practical importance**, it is based on providing a vision of how to link digital media platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the role they play in covering current events, especially in times of crisis, especially the devastating earthquake disaster that caused great damage to the old city of Marrakesh and its historical heritage, such as the destruction of homes and main roads. Historical buildings and ancient tourist attractions, the most important of which is the Tinmel Mosque, the symbol of the state, and the collapse of the city walls dating back to the Middle Ages, in addition to the fall of the Jewish Mellah neighborhood, in addition to the destruction of homes, the high toll of dead and wounded, and economic losses amounting to billions of dollars, which reflects the importance of these areas. Platforms cover natural disasters and current events related to them, as they are considered an important field of media in providing the latest news and developments about them to know the public's reactions to them in order to reach new and innovative theories and perceptions within the framework of the relationship between the public and new media.

Objectives of the Study

The Study aims to achieve a main goal: the rate of public dependence on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies as a source of information about natural disasters. The following sub-goals emerge from this goal:

- 1- Knowing the relationship between the rate of public dependence on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence

- technologies and the follow-up of the "Morocco earthquake" disaster.
- 2- Explaining the relationship between the public's follow-up of topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster through digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the degree of benefit from them.
 - 3- Detecting differences between the sample members' forms of interaction with topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies according to the geographical distribution variable.

The Study Sample

The study was conducted on a purposive sample of (520 Egyptian and Jordanian citizens following the Moroccan earthquake disaster, users of digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, aged (18: 30, 35 years, and above). The reasons for the researcher's selection of the Egyptian and Jordanian public sample as a segment it represents an active sector in the Egyptian and Jordanian media environment, given its connection to the place of Study of researchers, in addition to the fact that Egyptian and Jordanian citizens represent different age and educational levels of a diverse nature, males and females, and both audiences have a love of learning about topics related to the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, which it is predominantly pictorial in order to follow the economic, social, political and developmental effects of that disaster, which provides researchers with a sample that correctly represents the original community of young people within society. It was considered when selecting the sample to represent males and females, and according to the demographic variables, (20) Questionnaire (respondents) were deleted due to the lack of credibility in the numbering and honesty in providing information; the sample that was

used was (500) male and female respondents residing in the countries of "Egypt and Jordan," and it can be described as follows:

(1) Description of the study sample according to demographic variables (n=500)

Demographics Characteristics		F	%
Gender	Male	263	52.6%
	Female	237	47.4%
Age	Age 18: 30 years	275	55%
	35 years and over	225	45%
Educational level	Bachelor's degree	355	71%
	Postgraduate studies	145	29%
Geographical distribution	Egyptian audience	290	58%
	Jordanian public	210	42%
Total		500	100%

The data in the previous table indicates the following:

- **Gender:** Males came in first with a percentage of (52%), followed by females with a percentage of (47.4%), which indicates that males are more inclined towards following current events because the nature of participation requires a kind of boldness and initiative; in addition to the difference in the nature and type of the sample in Egyptian society.
- **Age:** The results showed that the age group (18: 30 years) had a high percentage of (55%), followed by the age group (35 years and above) with a percentage of (45%). This indicates increasing public awareness of the dangers of the devastating earthquake disaster that led to the occurrence of economic, material, and

human losses in the country, and therefore, they follow the events related to them on those platforms because of their enlightened mind to harm the issues that concern their Arab countries and because they have a mature culture and awareness to confront this phenomenon.

- **Educational level:** The results of the Study revealed that individuals with a bachelor's degree came in first at a rate of (71%), followed by postgraduate students at a rate of (29%), which shows us that Bachelor's degree students are the group most likely to pursue topics related to the "earthquake" disaster. Morocco" and interact with it because the concentration of Bachelor's degree students is higher than that of those with a post-university qualification.
- **Geographical Distribution:** The results of the Study revealed that the sample members residing in Egypt came first with a percentage of (58%), followed by those residing in Jordan with a percentage of (42%), which indicates that the residents of Egypt have a higher population density than those residing in Jordan.

Study population:

Egyptian and Jordanian citizens represent the human community following the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence techniques. The study sample ranges in age from (18 to 30 years, 35 years and over), and due to the large number of sites based on covering current events, the researchers found it difficult to implement on those sites. Hence, the researchers resorted to conducting an exploratory study on a sample of (12) individuals from Egyptian and Jordanian citizens to determine the most important of these platforms on the network. The digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence techniques based on covering current events according to the sample members' follow-up to them were as follows: Next: The "Facebook" platform is in the lead, followed by "YouTube," then "TikTok," followed by "Twitter," followed by "Instagram," and

finally "Snapchat." The previous result indicates that the "Facebook" and "YouTube" platforms had the highest follow-up rates.

The Limitations of the Study

- **Human limits:** represented by a sample of Egyptian and Jordanian citizens following the "Morocco earthquake" disaster via digital news supported by artificial intelligence techniques, aged from (18: 30, 35 years, and above).
- **Spatial boundaries:** Limited to Egyptian and Jordanian citizens who use digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies. These two countries were chosen due to their connection to the place where the researchers studied.
- **Thematic limits:** Limited to topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies. These topics are: "The destruction of buildings, homes, and archaeological monuments, the collapse of roads and services related to basic infrastructure, and the death toll rising to more than Thousands and hundreds of casualties, social disability for citizens in the affected areas, and serious economic losses estimated at billions of dollars."
- **Time limits:** The researchers conducted their Study on a sample of Egyptian and Jordanian citizens following the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence techniques. The study sample was applied in the period extending from 10/1/2023 to 11/30/2023.

Data Collection

A questionnaire newspaper was applied to a deliberate sample of (500) Egyptian and Jordanian citizens following the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster on digital news platforms supported by artificial

intelligence techniques, the study sample. The study was also applied in the period extending from 10/1/2023 until 11/30/ 2023.

The Research Design and Methodology

This study belongs to descriptive studies, which rely mainly on the use of the sample survey method, as it is the ideal way to obtain quantitative and qualitative data for all paragraphs of the questionnaire sheet, as the sample survey method contains the collection of respondents' data as essential parts to know the rate of public dependence on digital platforms supported by technologies artificial intelligence is a source of information about natural disasters, as the qualitative responses of the respondents depend on the interpretation of the digital results obtained because researchers in this type of study begin by monitoring and extracting results from the data obtained. The researchers followed this approach because it responds to the goal of the study in Knowing the public's attitudes towards following up on the damage resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies by measuring the responses of the respondents and the interaction of the sample members with the topics related to it, and based on that, the differences between the forms of the public's interaction with the topics related to it are inferred on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, according to the geographical distribution variable.

Study Variables

- Independent variable: natural disasters.
- Dependent variable: audience dependence on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies.

Cognitive Framework

- **First: Digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster:**

They are digital platforms supported by technologies that simulate human mental media capabilities that work to edit and formulate content automatically through algorithms without human intervention through a set of characteristics provided by computer programs in digital media (Mohamed, 2020).

Digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies are also an important media means for news coverage of the latest developments related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster in text, audio, and image, in addition to the role they play in achieving broad, interactive participation with the public.

"These platforms work to cover and broadcast news content that arouses the public's interest from the event site" (Sabri, 2022, p. 202). They include the interactive tools available on these platforms to make the user a recipient, sender, and sharer of information (Maher, 2020, p. 194), especially Covering topics related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster.

Digital media is based on producing news content and broadcasting it to the public from the event site using text, audio, and images (Sabri, 2022, p. 202).

There are many digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies used to cover topics related to the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, including:

- 1- **Facebook:** A social network that allows the media communicator to contribute to creating the event, transmitting it, and commenting with absolute freedom, in addition to the majority of institutions relying on it to transmit their news and programs to promote them and direct communication between the institution and its following audience (Bounjma, 2024, p.76).
- 2- **Twitter:** A blogging platform used for social communication using (380) characters through electronic devices regardless of spatial or temporal conditions, and in a more extensive, fast, and

accurate manner, with less cost and effort (Muhammad, 2019, p.130).

- 3- **YouTube:** It is one of the most popular websites that enable users to watch many published video clips that include various news and information that interest them at any time and place (Torres-Barzabal et al., 2020, p.12).
- 4- **How TikTok:** It is a smartphone application dedicated to recording and sharing videos between users (Herrman, 2019).
- 5- **WhatsApp:** An application that allows its users to send text and voice messages and files and share them across different groups in text, voice, and image, as well as make calls according to the user's needs (Sabri, 2023, p. 207).
- 6- **Instagram:** A social networking site that allows users to upload photos and videos, filter them digitally, and share them across groups (Al-Hawari & Muhammad, 2022, p. 234).

The public can benefit from digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies to follow the types of topics related to the "Morocco earthquake" disaster as follows:

- Destruction of buildings, homes, and archaeological monuments.
- Collapse of roads and services related to basic infrastructure.
- The death toll rose to more than a thousand, and hundreds were injured.
- The occurrence of a social deficit for citizens in the affected areas.
- Large economic losses estimated at billions of dollars.

Interacting with topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies:

It is to show the reactions that occur between users during the interaction process through comments, symbols, and various expressive forms provided by the algorithms of digital platforms (Kasroud, 2022, p.

29-30), as it is an appropriate measure to determine the effectiveness of the topics that institutions publish online and on social networking sites (Smith & Ronald, 2021, p. 255). Especially the interaction with the topics of "the destruction of buildings, homes, and archaeological monuments, the collapse of roads and services related to basic infrastructure, the death toll rising to more than a thousand and hundreds of injuries, social deficits for citizens in the affected areas, and serious economic losses estimated at billions of dollars."

Interactivity reflects the reactions of the receiving audience and the communicator about the content presented on digital platforms. It is based on providing many processes, such as wandering through programs or pages and making free choices compatible with their needs and interests, changing and modifying the content, and returning the results of this process to the broadcaster. The interaction process requires several tools to interact with other communication processes to achieve future and immediate goals. It is compatible with synchronous and asynchronous forms of communication (Ibrahim, 2023, pp. 618-619).

Forms of interaction with topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies:

There are many forms of interaction with topics related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, such as liking, commenting, and sharing (Mohamed, 2023, p. 249), including:

- 1- **Liked interaction:** It is a feature that allows the user to subscribe to various digital news pages, whether newspapers or television channels, to follow the latest news related to the content that interests them to interact with through those sites.
- 2- **Interact by commenting:** It means dialogue between users about the contents of issues that arouse their interest in the digital news pages that they follow to form different opinions about them, and it also represents one of the most important interactive contributions for the public (Mohamed, 2023, p. 249).

3- **Interact by Participation:** This feature allows users to exchange ideas about news material related to issues that interest them and share them from one site to another using text, audio, and images.

- **Second: The Theoretical Framework of the Study "Introduction to Symbolic Interaction"**

The study is based on the theory of symbolic interactionism, as it is closest to the content of the study that addresses the public's reliance on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies as a source of information about natural disasters, as a theoretical framework for explaining the interaction between users and the information presented on digital media.

The roots of this theory also extend to the sociologist George Herbert Mead, who is considered one of the most prominent founders of the interaction theory, which focuses on the processes of interaction and social communication that occur between users and the social environment on the network, assuming that the reality of the environment is based on the individual's interpretation of his surroundings. The relationship between the actor and his surroundings is variable and not fixed because the individual can interpret the world around him and read the meanings he imagines for his social and natural world (Khan, 2020).

Ervin Goffman believes that social interaction is based on the individual's ability to represent the roles between sender and receiver. The expectations that others have about our behavior are like texts that we must realize to represent them (Ariel & Avidar, 2015).

Symbolic interactivity focuses on the process of interaction and communication between users through language, symbols, the mind, and the self. Symbols are the meanings and connotations that indicate an individual's interaction with the content provided to satisfy his needs. They are social results that determine users' behavior patterns on the network. Symbolic social interaction is achieved through the communication function between users and the participation function that occurs through communication (Salama, 2018, p.12).

Dijck and Poell (2013) indicated that digital communication is based on the interconnection between users and symbols. Communication refers to the social and technical ability of online platforms to link content to users' activities on the network. Symbolic interactivity is also based on a set of basic concepts (Salem, 2032, p. 14), which are:

- **Interaction:** It is based on communication and mutual relationships between individuals.
- **Flexibility:** It means a person's ability to act in a set of circumstances in one way at one time.
- **Symbols:** These are interaction tools that individuals use to facilitate the process of communication and interaction between each other.

The theory of symbolic interactionism is also based on the following hypotheses (Salem, 2023, p. 14), **which are:**

- 1- The contribution of individuals to the shared meanings associated with symbols is a personal activity from which expected behavior patterns emerge. The awareness formed by the public from interaction with the topics presented by digital media appears in the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral responses they have from interaction with its content, ultimately forming interactive digital communication behavior.
- 2- Individuals act toward things based on what those things mean to them. Meanings are a product of social interaction in human society through an interpretation process that each individual uses in his dealings with the signals he encounters (Nawa, 2016, p. 57).

Symbolic interactive refers to planned efforts in designing media websites, programs, and content that allow the user to the greatest extent of participation in the process of communication and freely choose from the content and services available on digital networks according to his needs and interests (Sobhi, 2021, p. 93).

The scientific literature reveals Various attempts to classify interaction with information related to the "Morocco earthquake disaster" on interactive digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence tools. A study was conducted (Mohamed, 2024, p. 392). The study focused on identifying the level of the public's awareness of the impact of algorithmic systems on the distribution of news content on Facebook and its relationship to their interactive behavior (Abdel Basset, 2023, p. 489) to know the role of digital media in raising awareness of the issues of artificial intelligence technologies as a concept and areas of their employment, a study was conducted (Makady, 2023). By identifying the role of digital platforms supported by algorithms in educating and encouraging the public to consume news and interact with it actively, the study by (Nechushtai et al., 2023) was concerned with Knowing the extent of the ability of digital platforms equipped with algorithmic systems (Facebook, YouTube, Twitter) in helping American participants search for news. Abdel Ghaffar (2022) identified the mechanisms and forms of audience interaction with reports of a social nature on the digital platforms of foreign Arabic-speaking channels.

The model of Williams Rice and Rogers indicates that the interactive process in the virtual world includes three main basic dimensions: "Control of communication," mutual communication between parties. The communication process with the same opportunities available to them (Mutual Discourse) is the exchange of roles between the sender and the receiver (McMillan & Hawing, 2013).

The theory of symbolic interactivity will be applied in light of our study to determine the extent of the public's reliance on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies as a source of information about natural disasters. Users act in the media through what the contents of the topics presented on the scene mean to them to attract the public's attention, to infer the meanings of the interactive symbols that it is used by the public on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, in order to know the patterns of public

interaction with content related to the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, as the theory of symbolic interactionism is linked in the current study, to testing the relationship between the rate of public dependence on digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and following up on the "earthquake" disaster in Morocco, in addition to demonstrating the relationship between the public's follow-up of a type of topic related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the degree of benefit from them, in addition to revealing the differences between the forms of interaction of sample members with topics related to damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster. Through digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, according to the geographical distribution variable, which indicates employing factors influencing symbolic interactivity such as demographic variables and the nature and type of topics to achieve the study's objectives, hypotheses, and questions.

Validity and reliability procedures for the questionnaire sheet:

- To test the questionnaire sheet's validity and reliability and ensure its ability to achieve the study's objectives, the form was presented to the arbitrators in the media field to verify its apparent validity. In light of the observations made by the arbitrators, the questionnaire sheet was modified and implemented during the year 2023, during the extended period. From 10/1/2023 until 11/30/2023, in calculating the stability of the questionnaire results, the researchers relied on the retest method, where after collecting the data, the researchers conducted a study on (5%) of the total field study items (20) items using a coefficient "Cranach's Alpha coefficient," which indicates that there is a high degree of consistency between the respondents' responses, and the following table shows us the calculation of the value of the reliability coefficient for the questionnaire sheet:

Table (2) Cronbach's alpha coefficient to measure the reliability of the questionnaire (n=500)

The field	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
Cronbach's alpha coefficient for all items of the questionnaire	0.90

The table data indicates the following:

- The value of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was high (0.91), which means the reliability coefficient is high. It also indicates no significant differences in the respondents' responses and that the questionnaire sheet is valid for application.

Statistical Analysis

- Simple statistical ratios and frequencies were used for the questionnaire questions, the Pearson correlation coefficient (person) to measure the intensity and direction of the relationship between the variables, and the (T-Test) test to find differences between the averages of the sample members' interaction with topics related to the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, and the (Cronbach's alpha) coefficient to measure the stability of the questionnaire sheet.

The Results

The field study sample represented the age group of (18: 30, 35 years, and older) of Egyptian and Jordanian citizens who use digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, as it included a sample of (500) individuals, in addition to testing the results of the validity of the hypotheses and linking them to the questions and objectives of the study. The following is a presentation of the study results:

Table (3) The average dependency of the sample members on the digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies to follow

up on the damages resulting from the "Moroccan earthquake" disaster (n = 500)

N	Reliance Rate	F	%
1	Highly adopted	203	40.6%
2	Moderate adapted	153	30.6%
3	Weakly adapted	144	28.8%
Total		500	100%

The data of the previous table indicates the following:

- (40.6%) of the sample confirmed that they rely to a large extent on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies to follow up on the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, followed by reliance to a moderate degree by (30.6%), and finally reliance to a weak degree by (28.8%). This indicates the keenness of these platforms supported by algorithms to evaluate news content related to current events and present it to the public in different ways and formats according to specific criteria to attract the largest possible audience, in addition to their keenness to follow up on knowledge of the latest developments related to the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, which led to the destruction of dozens of people. Villages, cities, regions, and archaeological sites from the historic city of Marrakesh, in addition to thousands of deaths and injuries and the displacement of thousands of residents, which is consistent with the study of Nechushtai et al. (2023). This is confirmed: Professionally produced news on some platforms constitutes the basic pillars that influence the political orientations of the public when searching for information, such as the Fox News platform in particular.

Table (4) The degree to which respondents follow the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies (n = 500)

N	Degree of follow-up	F	%
1	I follow to a large extent	185	37%
2	I follow up moderately	166	33.2%
3	I follow up to a weak degree	149	29.8%
Total			

The data in the previous table indicates the following:

- (37%) of the sample confirmed that they are following the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies to a large extent, followed by follow-up to a moderate degree (33.2%), and finally follow-up to a weak degree (29.8%), so It can be said that they are exposed to topics related to the "Morocco earthquake" disaster with great intensity, because they realize how important it is to them, resulting from the landslide that led to the destruction of ancient villages on the tops of the hills to become disaster areas, in addition to the closure of the road leading to the small town of "Asni," located in the Atlas Mountains.

Table (5) The sampling personnel are exposed to the quality of topics related to the damages resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster through the newsletter backed by artificial intelligence technologies (n = 300), (n = 290), (n = 210), (n = 500) (You can choose more than one alternative)

N		Topics related to the damages resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster	Egyptian Audience		Jordanian Audience		Total	
			F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Destruction of buildings, houses, and archaeological monuments	71	24.48%	46	21.90%	117	23.4%	
2	Collapse of roads and services related to basic infrastructure	55	18.96%	57	27.14%	112	23.4%	
3	The death toll rose to more than a thousand, and hundreds were injured	71	24.48%	23	10.95%	94	22.4%	
4	Social deficit for citizens in affected areas	45	15.53%	57	27.14%	102	18.8%	
5	Serious economic losses estimated at billions of dollars occurred	48	16.55%	27	12.87%	75	20.4%	
Total		290	100%	210	100%	500	15%	

The data in the previous table indicates the following:

- (23.4%) of the sample confirmed that they are monitoring the destruction of buildings, homes, and archaeological monuments among the topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, followed by the collapse of roads and services related to basic infrastructure at a rate of (22.4%), and then the occurrence of a social deficit for citizens in The affected areas increased by (20.4%), followed by a rise in the death toll to more than a thousand and hundreds of injuries by (18.8%), and finally serious economic losses estimated at billions of dollars by (15%).
- **In the Egyptian public's follow-up of topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster**

through digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies: (24.48%) of the sample confirmed that they are following the destruction of buildings, homes, and archaeological monuments, the death toll rising to more than a thousand, and hundreds of wounded among topics related to the damages resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, followed by the collapse of roads and services related to the basic infrastructure by (18.96%), and then serious economic losses estimated at billions of dollars by (16.55%), and finally a social deficit of citizens in the affected areas (15.53%), which indicates: They are interested in following up on topics related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence tools, as they are characterized by the speed of transmitting news and information related to it, as well as their awareness of the extent of the damage resulting from that disaster, which led to the occurrence of human, material, and heritage losses, in addition to the influx of many wounded into Marrakesh hospitals, which prompted the authorities to call on citizens to donate blood, in accordance with a study Muhammad (2024). This showed that the sample members are highly aware of the algorithm systems that distribute news content on Facebook platforms, although they do not realize enough because there are human interventions behind this machine that can affect the decisions of the submitted content.

- **In the Jordanian public's follow-up of topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster through digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies:** (27.14%) of the sample confirmed that they are following the collapse of roads and services related to basic infrastructure, the occurrence of a social deficit for citizens in the affected areas, Followed by the destruction of buildings, homes, and archaeological monuments by (21.90%), then serious

economic losses estimated at billions of dollars by (12.87%), and finally the death toll rose to more than a thousand and hundreds of wounded by (10.95%), so it can be said: They are following the information related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster through digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies to know the latest developments related to it, to understand the events taking place around them so that they can interpret them, as they are renewable platforms that publish everything real-time about the events related to that disaster, which is what made these sites a distinguished position among the current media for its ability to attract the masses to it from all groups, as well as the contribution of these platforms in educating the public about how to deal with crises and disasters and achieve their societal participation by guiding volunteer teams with methods and methods of access to remote areas most affected in an area in the Atlas Mountains to help the affected people In the affected areas, which is compatible with the study of Nishoshtai et al. (2023). This revealed differences between members of the in-kind regarding the political trends of the subjects presented.

Table (6) The degree to which sample members benefited from following up on the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies (n = 500)

N	Degree of benefit	F	%
1	Benefited greatly	215	43%
2	Benefited moderately	150	30%

3	Benefited to a weak degree	135	27%
	Total	500	100%

The data in the previous table indicates the following:

- (43%) of the sample confirmed that they benefited greatly from following up on the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, followed by benefiting to a great extent (30%), and finally benefiting to a moderate degree (27%). Therefore, it can be said that they depend on following the media material provided to them due to the importance of the role played by these platforms, as they are renewable platforms that publish everything current about current events, and therefore, they look at them to find out the latest news and developments related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster. Which led to a rise in the death toll and more bodies being recovered from under the rubble.

Table (7) Digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies that sample members are keen to follow to obtain news related to the "Morocco earthquake" disaster (n=500) (You can choose more than one alternative)

N	Digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies	F	%
1	Facebook platform	135	27%
2	YouTube platform	95	19%

3	Twitter platform	93	18.6%
4	Tik Tok platform	85	17%
5	Instagram platform	49	9.8%
6	Snapchat platform	43	8.6%
	Total	500	100%

The data in the previous table indicates the following:

- (46%) of the sample confirmed that they follow the "Facebook" platform to obtain news related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, followed by "YouTube" (19%), then "Twitter" (18.6%), followed by "Tik Tok" (17%), followed by "Instagram" by (9.8%), and finally "Snapchat" by (8.6%), which indicates: the ability of digital news platforms supported by simulation robots to produce and broadcast news content to meet public protests in the natural language that simulates human intelligence with natural language that mimics human intelligence, as well as continuous updating of the news material to provide the opportunity to reach the largest window of interaction between platform-based chatbots and the audience. Makady (2023) revealed a relationship between algorithmic awareness, self-monitoring, and active news consumption on Facebook.

(8) Elements of attracting respondents towards the following topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies (n = 290), (n = 210), (n = 500) (You can choose more than one alternative)

N	Attraction Elements	F	%
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1	Video clips related to the topics of the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster	133	26.6%
2	Thematic images	96	19.2%
3	Personal photos	64	12.8%
4	Studies and Research	74	14.8%
5	Analysis and comments of free discussion panels related to disaster topics in Morocco	133	26.6%
Total		500	100%

The data in the previous table indicates the following:

- (26.6%) of the sample confirmed that they are attracted to the following video clips related to the topics of the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, analysis and comments for free discussion panels related to disaster topics in Morocco, which indicates the nature of digital news platforms that focus on providing visual content that is appropriate for the nature of the audience using these platforms, due to the nature of the contents related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, which made it capture the public's attention by following the content provided to them through these platforms, which includes all the details of the disaster following the directions and policies of the Kingdom of Morocco that establishes the devastating earthquake disaster. The priority of its agenda is to re-house the affected people and take care of the most affected groups, which affects the country's economic growth balance because these news platforms aim to attract the largest number of viewers, followed by objective images with a percentage of (19.2%), which shows us that they are not inclined to public reading for events related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, given that the reader or viewer is satisfied with pictures that are an alternative to a thousand

words and then studies and Research at a rate of (14.8%), which indicates that digital news platforms are keen to provide studies and Research to achieve good results related to the damages resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, so that the target audience understands the amount of material and human losses to society in order to deal with these crises with caution, and finally, personal photos (12.8%), and this can be explained: that they are connected to following up on events related to the events related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster.

This is because digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence tools present events that include images that illustrate the effects of the devastating earthquake disaster that led to the destruction of buildings, roads, and the country's infrastructure, as well as economic losses estimated at billions of dollars.

Table (9) Respondents' forms of interaction with topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies (n=290), (n=210), (n=500) (You can choose more than one alternative)

	N	Forms of interaction	Egyptian Audience		Jordanian Audience		Total	
			F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Like	36	12.41%	35	16.68%	71	14.2%	
2	Comment	181	62.41%	125	59.52%	306	61.2%	

N	Forms of interaction	Egyptian	Jordanian		Total		
		Audiance	F	%	F	%	
3	Share	73	25.18%	50	23.80%	123	24.6%
	Total	290	100%	210	100%	500	15%

The data in the previous table indicates the following:

- (61.2%) of individuals confirmed that They prefer to interact by commenting on topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, followed by interaction by sharing (24.6%), and then interaction by liking (14.2%).
- **Regarding interaction with likes:**
 (16.68%) of the Jordanian public confirmed that they prefer to interact with admiration with topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster through digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, compared to (12.41%) for the Egyptian public, and this indicates: that These sites enjoy a high degree of credibility among their audience who follow topics related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster as a result of the continuous updating of the content provided to them on those sites, following the study of Abdel Basset (2023) which indicated: Individuals of the sample interact with media messages that include products and services that rely on artificial intelligence technologies.
- **Regarding interaction by commenting:** (62.41%) of the Egyptian public confirmed that they prefer to interact by commenting on topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, compared to (59.52%) of the Jordanian public, which indicates: that digital news platforms provide diverse content that is

accurate and objective and includes all aspects related to the devastating "Morocco earthquake" disaster, as well as its connection to the lives of individuals, which enhances the trust and credibility of the public in those platforms and works to strengthen their role in educating the public, which is what made them tend towards using the commentary tool is used to express their opinions regarding topics related to the devastating earthquake disaster, as it represents the common dialogue aspect between those platforms and their interactive audiences, which achieves broad public participation between those platforms and their audiences, in accordance with the study of Abdel Ghaffar (2022) which indicated: There is a statistically significant relationship between the availability of interactive tools and the way respondents interact with reports of a social nature published through the digital platforms of foreign Arabic-speaking channels.

- **In interaction with share:** (25.18%) of the Egyptian public confirmed that they prefer to interact with admiration with topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, compared to (23.80%) of the Jordanian public, which indicates: They share topics related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster on their pages, which leads to an increase in page follow-up rates for non-followers due to the importance of the issue to them, which is consistent with the study of Tafesse and Wood (2021) which showed: There is a significant positive interaction between the volume of content and areas of interest, a result that indicates that influencers with diverse interests can stimulate greater engagement from followers by sharing more content on their social media accounts.

Table (10) Sample members' follow-up to news sources related to topics related to the damages resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies (n = 500)

N	Sources of news related to the "Morocco earthquake" disaster	F	%
1	Newspapers and news agencies on the Internet	96	19.2%
2	Reports of correspondents and delegates	117	23.4%
3	Responsible sources	65	13%
4	Social networking sites	81	16.2%
5	Conferences and seminars	65	13%
6	Interviews with guests inside the studio	35	7%
7	Experts and specialists	41	8.2%
Total		500	100%

The data in the previous table indicates the following:

- (23.4%) of the sample confirmed that they prefer to follow the reports of correspondents and delegates about the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster. This indicates that digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence tools are keen to provide various forms of news accompanied by visual material through the network of their correspondents on the site. The event, which affects the viewing audience to a great extent, has a significant impact on viewers as it covers current events from the event sites, which reflects the confirmation of the credibility of the topics presented to it on those platforms, followed by newspapers and news agencies on the Internet with a percentage of (19.2%), so it can be said that they rely on it due to representing an important source for obtaining information related to topics related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, given that it is characterized by speed in conveying current events because it has a network of correspondents spread throughout the world, and then social networking sites at a rate of (16.2%). It was followed by responsible sources, conferences, and seminars at a rate of (13%), followed by experts and specialists at a rate of (8.2%), and finally, meetings with guests inside the studio at a rate of (7%) indicating that

it is an important attraction for obtaining news and information from its source and knowing their opinions directly.

Results of the hypotheses test

- The first hypothesis: This hypothesis states that there is a statistically significant correlation between the rate of public reliance on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the follow-up of the "Morocco earthquake" disaster.

Table (11) The relationship between the rate of public dependence on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the follow-up of the "Morocco earthquake" disaster. (n=500)

Variables	The rate of audience adoption on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies		
	The value of T	The significance level	The significance level
Follow-up of the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster	0.59 **	0.01	0.05

* Significant at the level of (0.01)
the level (0.05)

** Significant at

The data in the table above indicates the following:

- Using the correlation coefficient (person): It was revealed that there is a statistically significant correlation between the rate of public reliance on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and following up on the "Morocco earthquake" disaster. The value of the correlation coefficient reached (0.59**), which is significant at the level of (0.01).), which indicates that the greater the reliance on digital news platforms supported by technology, the more follow-up to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster will be to

know the latest developments on related topics. This comes in light of the high number of deaths and injuries and the continued search for survivors by local and international rescue teams underneath. The rubble, in addition to the influx of many citizens to health centers to donate blood in response to the authorities' call to treat injured people who need blood transfusions.

- **The second hypothesis:** This hypothesis states that There is a statistically significant correlation between the public's follow-up of specific topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster through digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the degree of benefit from them.

Table (12) The relationship between the public's follow-up of specific topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the degree of benefit from them (n = 500)

Variables	Public follow-up of topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies		
	The value of T	The significance level	The significance level
the degree of benefit from them	0.33 **	0.01	0.05

* Significant at the level of (0.01)

** Significant at the level (0.05)

The data in the table above indicates the following:

- Using the correlation coefficient (person): It was revealed that there is a statistically significant correlation between the public's follow-

up of specific topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the degree of benefit from them. The value of the correlation coefficient reached (0.33**), which is a function at the level of (0.01); this indicates that the more topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster are followed through digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies, the greater the degree of benefit from them, which shows us: They are more aware of the disaster they are following on those platforms, and the resulting about the devastating earthquakes that led to the closure of the road leading to the small town of Asni, located in the Atlas Mountains, as well as the destruction of ancient villages located on hilltops and areas near the historic city of Marrakesh, turning them into rubble.

The third hypothesis states that there are statistically significant differences between the sample members' forms of interaction with topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies according to the geographical distribution variable.

Table (13) Significance of statistical differences between the sample members' forms of interaction with topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies according to the geographical distribution variable (n=500)

Scale	Egyptian Audience		Jordanian Audience		the value of (T)	Significance Level	Significance Level
	Mean	Total ranks	Mean	Total ranks			
					3.77**		

Forms of interaction of sample members with topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster	2.20	0.81	1.81			0.01	0.05
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* Significant at the level of (0.01)

** Significant at the level (0.05)

The data in the previous table indicates the following:

- **Using the T-Test:** It became clear that there were statistically significant differences between the forms of interaction of sample members with topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence techniques according to the geographical distribution variable and in the direction of the Egyptian public, and it amounted to the value of $t = (3.77^{**})$, which is significant at the level of (0.01), which indicates: the impact of the news content on the importance of the audience's interaction with the news and the transformation of the receiver into a sender and sharer of information on his page. Also, the level of confidence of males is higher than that of females because they more follow up on issues related to the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster, and this comes in light of the Moroccan authorities' assessment of the extent of the destruction caused to archaeological sites and the development of a special strategy for their restoration, in addition to activating the urgent program to shelter those affected and take care of them as a result of the devastation caused by the earthquakes that struck the country.

Conclusion

- Through the study, the researchers tried to find out the relationship between the rate of the public's reliance on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the follow-up of the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, as well as to know the differences between the forms of interaction of the sample members with it, because interactive media has a major impact on shaping the public's attitudes towards current events, especially the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, which led to the collapse of homes, heritage buildings, and basic road infrastructure, in addition to material and human losses estimated at billions of dollars, so it has become necessary to pay attention to topics related to current events that arouse the public's interest in order to know their reactions to them. It asked questions to find solutions to reach innovative theories and perceptions within the framework of the relationship between the public and the media. The study reached a set of results, the most important of which are:

- The vast majority of the sample confirmed that they are following the destruction of buildings, homes, and archaeological monuments among the topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, followed by the collapse of roads and services related to basic infrastructure, and then the occurrence of a social deficit for citizens in the affected areas, followed by an increase in the death toll for more than thousands and hundreds of casualties, and finally serious economic losses estimated at billions of dollars.

- The results showed that there is a statistically significant correlation between the rate of public reliance on digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the follow-up of the "Morocco earthquake" disaster, which indicates that digital news platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies have performed their assigned role to the fullest in

presenting the topics that members care about participants in it to know the latest developments around it, which comes in light of the high number of dead and wounded and the local and international rescue teams continuing to search for survivors under the rubble, in addition to the influx of many citizens to health centers to donate blood in response to the authorities call to treat the injured who need blood transfusions, which is reflected in to attract the following audience towards participating in overcoming the opinion and finding solutions to get out of this disaster.

- The results showed that there is a statistically significant correlation between the public's follow-up of the quality of topics related to damage resulting from an earthquake disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies and the degree of benefit from them, which shows us: they are more aware of the disaster that they follow on those platforms, resulting from the devastating earthquakes that caused To close the road leading to the small town of Asni, located in the Atlas Mountains, in addition to destroying the ancient villages located on the tops of the hills and the areas near the historic city of Marrakesh, turning them into rubble.

- The results showed that there were statistically significant differences between the forms of interaction of sample members with topics related to the damage resulting from the "Morocco Earthquake" disaster via digital platforms supported by artificial intelligence technologies according to the geographical distribution variable and in the direction of the Egyptian audience, which indicates: the influence of news content on the importance of audience interaction with the news and turning into a receiver into a sender and sharer of information on his page, this comes in light of the Moroccan authorities assessing the extent of the destruction caused to archaeological sites and developing a

special strategy for their restoration, in addition to activating the urgent program to shelter those affected and take care of them as a result of the destruction caused by the earthquakes throughout the country.

The study also reached a set of recommendations, the most important of which are:

- Emphasizing the need for digital news platforms to conduct media campaigns to educate the public about the dangers of natural disasters, with interest in establishing a national governmental center that includes all activities at the country level to deal with disasters and crises, with the need to adopt guiding principles for reducing disaster risks and preparing for them by encouraging civil society initiatives to confront these phenomena with various methods to provide relief to those affected and provide support to them, in addition to rebuilding and general rehabilitation of the affected areas, while making use of meetings with experts in the natural sciences and geology to ask questions and proposed solutions to confront this phenomenon, which reflects the importance of public interaction with topics related to this phenomenon which is based on enriching the interactive discussion on digital news platforms between communicators and the public, to reach new and innovative theories and perceptions within the framework of the relationship between the public and digital media.

Research Proposals

In light of the study, the researcher presents a set of proposals, which are:

- The role of artificial intelligence applications in educating the public about the risks of natural disasters.
- Public trends towards following the social impacts of the Morocco earthquake disaster on the GPT chat platform.

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